

**A STUDY ON INTERPRETATION OF HISTOPATHOLOGY OF
CARCINOMA RECTUM IN AYURVEDA - A CASE STUDY****Dr. Udit Parveen^{1*}, Dr. Hemen Kalita²**

¹PG Scholar, Department of Roga Nidan, Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital,
Guwahati-14.

²Associate Professor, Department of Roga Nidan, Government Ayurvedic College and
Hospital, Guwahati-14.

Article Received on 26 Sept. 2025,
Article Revised on 06 October 2025,
Article Published on 16 October 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17364544>

Corresponding Author*Dr. Udit Parveen**

PG Scholar, Department of Roga
Nidan, Government Ayurvedic
College and Hospital, Guwahati-14.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Udit Parveen*,
Dr. Hemen Kalita (2025). A Study On
Interpretation Of Histopathology Of
Carcinoma Rectum In Ayurveda - A Case
Study. World Journal of Pharmaceutical
Research, 14(20), XXX-XXX.

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ABSTRACT

Conventional treatment of cancer had got many challenges. So many patients opt for alternative treatment like Ayurveda and therefore visit Ayurvedic hospital, practitioners, etc. for their treatment. But for Ayurvedic treatment, a proper Ayurvedic evidence-based diagnosis is important. For evidence-based diagnosis, histopathological report needed to be interpreted in Ayurveda. So, the histopathological report of a certain case of Carcinoma Rectum was studied in the light of Ayurveda to find out the interpretation of the disease. In this regard a clinical case study was done on a certain case of Carcinoma Rectum who came to Cancer Speciality Clinic of Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Guwahati. Her histopathological report was studied and a possible interpretation in Ayurveda was made.

KEYWORDS: Cancer, evidence-based diagnosis, alternative treatment, Ayurveda, histopathology.

INTRODUCTION

The traditional approach to cancer treatment like chemotherapy, radiation and surgery face numerous challenges. To reduce or minimize the negative effects of conventional cancer treatments and to improve the quality of life, many patients today opt for Ayurvedic treatment as an adjunct, palliative or stand-alone treatment. Accurate diagnosis according to Ayurvedic

principles is essential for effective Ayurvedic treatment. A clinical case study was done on a certain case of Carcinoma Rectum who came to Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Guwahati-14 dated 31st august 2023 having OPD registration number 4***9. Her histopathological report was studied and an interpretation of the findings in Ayurveda were made after a thorough literary review related to the study to construct a possible evidence-based diagnosis.

CASE NOTE

A female patient aged 73 years came with a chief complain of bleeding per rectum along with weight loss and generalised weakness since July, 2023. She was a known case of hypertension under regular medication. There was no associated pain or any other complain. She visited nearby hospital whereby she was diagnosed as a case of Carcinoma Rectum. She was advised further treatment for the same but she refused to do modern conventional treatment. So, she came to Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Guwahati opting for traditional medicine as stand- alone treatment. Personal histories reveal her diet is mixed having katu amla Pradhan tridosha, ajeernabhojan & adhyasana present, aharasakti, abhyavarana shakti & jarana shakti madhyam, adequate sleep, urine clear, stool passes 1-2 times per day sometimes with blood, with no any addiction or family history. On physical examination, the patient was observed to be having mild pallor and her systemic examination reveals no any abnormalities. **Astaveedh Pariksha** reveals nadi to be Pitta- Kaphaj, mala samyak pravritti with on and off sarakta, mutra samyak pravritti, jihva aalipita, sabda samyak, sparsha samanya, drik samanya, akriti cintamati.

Her histopathological report showed the following findings:

Nature of specimen- tissue from distal rectum to anal canal.

Gross- specimen consists of multiple bits of greyish brown tissue aggregate measuring (0.7 x 0.5) cm.

Microscopic examination- section shows multiple fragments of tissue lined by dysplastic stratified squamous epithelium with infiltration to the sub epithelial tissue. The neoplastic cells have moderate amount of cytoplasm with irregular, pleomorphic hyperchromatic nuclei and inconspicuous nucleoli in few. Stroma shows dense infiltration by chronic inflammatory cells. Large area of haemorrhage and necrosis with pigment noted.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

The histopathological report was studied for gross and microscopic examination. Every findings were evaluated and a possible Ayurvedic interpretation as mentioned in Ayurvedic classics was made. Since the specimen was taken from distal rectum to anal canal, it can be interpreted in Ayurveda as guda.^[1] On gross examination, the specimen consists of multiple bits of greyish- brown tissue aggregates measuring 0.7 x 0.5 cm, which can be interpreted as kshudra mamsa dhatu having akriti of 1.33 x 0.95 Angula.^[2] Moreover, the colour of the tissue can be interpreted as syava- aruna varna (shown in fig.I), indicating vata prakop.^[3] On microscopic examination, dysplastic cells were found. Here cells can be considered as paramanu in Ayurveda.^[4] So dysplastic cells were correlated as vikrit paramanu^[4] (shown in fig.II). Various cytomorphology of neoplastic cells can be described under vikrit vayu karma^[3] Presence of haemorrhage and necrosis indicate dushit rakta (shown in fig. I). On the basis of the above discussion, the outcome of the disease can be evaluated as followed:

Site of the disease: guda.

Gross examination: reveals vata dushit mamsa dhatu of guda.

Microscopic examination: reveals vikrit vayu karma and rakta dushti of guda.

So, the histopathological findings in this case can be understood in Ayurveda as **vata pradhan mamsa- rakta dushit guda roga**. Consequently, the principle of treatment may be adopted to pacify vayu and address the mamsa and rakta dhatu dushti. This can be valuable for an evidence- based diagnosis in the treatment of cancer within Ayurveda.

Fig. 1: shows Ayurvedic interpretation of the gross findings of squamous cell carcinoma of rectum.

Fig. 2: Shows Ayurvedic interpretation of the microscopic findings of squamous cell carcinoma of rectum.

CONCLUSION

The evidence-based diagnosis of the present case of carcinoma rectum, based on histopathological examination may be interpreted in Ayurveda as *vata pradhan mamsa-rakta dushit guda roga*. This is merely a case report of a single study. However, future research on this topic is crucial to develop a comprehensive protocol.

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